

Reactor Kinetics Measurements of a HALEU TRISO-Fueled Critical Experiment

Cole Kostelac^{1,2,*}, Theresa Cutler¹, Nicholas Thompson¹, Nicholas Whitman¹, Christopher Campbell³, Nader Satvat³, Ayodeji Alajo²

¹Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM;

²Missouri University of Science and Technology, Rolla, MO; ³Kairos Power, Alameda, CA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804096

ABSTRACT

TRISO (TRi-structural ISOtropic) fuel is being considered by many advanced reactor designers for its superior performance in normal and accident scenarios. The Kairos Power FHR (KP-FHR) is one such design that utilizes TRISO fuel. While transport codes are well validated for estimations of reactor kinetics parameters for traditional UO₂ light water moderated reactors, there is significantly less validation for graphite moderated TRISO fueled systems. In this work, we perform reactor kinetics measurements using neutron noise methods on the THETA experiment within the Deimos testbed, representing the first criticality of a TRISO fueled system in the United States in over 30 years. Specifically, we measure the prompt neutron decay constant for three delayed critical configurations. Experimental values agree with MCNP6.3 simulations using various nuclear data libraries within 5%. A general trend of increasing simulation error is observed as the configurations neutron energy spectrum become more intermediate.

Keywords: Reactor Physics, Criticality Experiment, HALEU, TRISO, Neutron Noise, Flux Profile

1. INTRODUCTION

With the accelerating electrification of the transportation sector and the rapid growth of data centers, there is an increasing demand for reliable, abundant, and carbon-free electricity. In response, both governmental and private stakeholders are recognizing nuclear energy as a key component of the future energy mix. Advanced reactor concepts are being developed to meet this demand, offering improved safety margins and higher fuel utilization compared to conventional light water reactors (LWRs), which currently supply the majority of nuclear-generated electricity.

Kairos Power is advancing one such design: the KP-FHR, a fluoride-salt-cooled, graphite-moderated reactor that utilizes high-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU) TRISO fuel. HALEU enables higher burnup than conventional low-enriched uranium (LEU), while TRISO fuel particles provide enhanced accident tolerance by containing fission products at significantly higher temperatures than traditional UO₂ fuel [1].

The development of advanced reactor systems introduces new modeling challenges and requires validation of the computational tools used to simulate both steady-state and transient behavior. Two key parameters that govern a reactor's dynamic response to reactivity perturbations are the prompt neutron generation time (Λ) and the effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}). While these parameters are well characterized for conventional systems (such as LWRs) using validated transport codes like MCNP and Serpent, experimental data is scarce for graphite-moderated, TRISO-fueled reactors.

Neutron noise techniques offer a powerful method for inferring these kinetic parameters. In particular, the prompt neutron decay constant (α) at delayed critical ($k_{\text{eff}} = 1$) provides a means to estimate the

*kostelac@lanl.gov

ratio $-\beta_{\text{eff}}/\Lambda$. This relationship enables experimental determination of relative changes in the prompt neutron generation time, which can then be compared against transport code predictions. In recent years, these kinetic parameters have been measured in a variety of zero power critical systems, including light-water moderated reactors like the CROCUS [2], IPEN/MB-01 [3], and MINERVE [4] research reactors, as well as fast-spectrum systems such as the VENUS-F reactor [5] and the CERBERUS critical experiment [6]. In contrast, kinetic measurements for graphite-moderated, TRISO-fueled systems remain largely absent from the literature.

To address the gap in experimental validation data, Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), in collaboration with Kairos Power, conducted a zero-power critical experiment at the National Criticality Experiments Research Center (NCERC). The experiment, known as THETA, was performed on the Comet vertical lift machine-previously used for the KRUSTY experiment under NASA's Kilopower space reactor program [7][8]. THETA was designed to support validation of k_{eff} calculation in transport simulations for HALEU TRISO-fueled, graphite-moderated systems. The experiment was fueled by TRISO fuel kernels compacted into a graphite matrix known as a fuel compact (see Figure 1). 19 of these fuel compacts were stacked to create hundreds of fuel rods. These fuel rods were moderated by graphite and reflected by beryllium metal to achieve criticality.

Figure 1. TRISO Kernel and Compacts used to fuel THETA experiment

The THETA experiment included various configurations of this graphite-moderated, beryllium-reflected array of TRISO fuel rods, with and without high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and borated HDPE rods. Neutron noise measurements were conducted on three configurations: one with no HDPE nor borated HDPE, one with HDPE, and one with both HDPE and borated HDPE. By selectively introducing and removing HDPE and borated HDPE rods, the hydrogen and boron concentrations within the system were varied. These changes significantly impacted the prompt neutron generation time, and the resulting effects were captured through neutron noise measurements.

The experimentally observed changes in prompt neutron decay constant were then compared to predictions from MCNP6.3 using various nuclear data libraries, providing valuable insight into the accuracy of these tools when applied to non-traditional reactor configurations [9].

2. THEORY

The zero-power reactor transfer function (ZPTF) of a point reactor model is obtained by taking the Laplace transform of the neutron population dynamics governed by the so-called point kinetics equations. These equations with M delayed neutron groups are given as

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dn(t)}{dt} &= \frac{\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda} n(t) + \sum_{j=1}^M \lambda_j C_j(t), \\ \frac{dC_j(t)}{dt} &= \frac{\beta_j}{\Lambda} n(t) - \lambda_j C_j(t), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, M.\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Where $n(t)$ is the neutron population, $C_j(t)$ is the j^{th} delayed neutron precursor concentration, ρ is reactivity, β_{eff} the effective delayed neutron fraction, Λ the prompt neutron generation time, and λ_j the j^{th} precursor decay constant.

The standard form of the ZPTF is given by [10] as

$$H(\omega) = \frac{\Lambda}{i\omega\Lambda - (\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}}) - \sum \frac{\lambda_j \beta_j}{\lambda_j + i\omega}}.\tag{2}$$

3. METHODS

In order to relate the ZPTF to an experimentally observable quantity, we use the Cohn- α formalism. This is achieved by estimating the auto power spectral density (APSD) of a neutron sensitive detectors signal. The APSD of the dependent signal is defined as the Fourier transform of its auto-correlation function and is related to the ZPTF as

$$APSD \equiv \mathcal{F} \left\{ \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T c(t)c(t+\tau)dt \right\} = 2\bar{c}^2 \frac{D}{F} |H(\omega)|^2 + b.\tag{3}$$

Where D is the Diven factor, F is the integral fission rate (fission per second) and \bar{c} is the mean count rate during the measurement. Above frequencies of the shortest lived delayed neutron precursors ($\omega > \lambda_M$), the count rate normalized APSD is fit to a Lorentzian distribution of the form

$$\frac{APSD}{\bar{c}^2} = 2 \frac{D}{F} \frac{1}{1 + (\frac{\omega}{\alpha})^2} + b, \quad \alpha = \frac{\rho - \beta_{\text{eff}}}{\Lambda}\tag{4}$$

where ω is the angular frequency (radians per second). The break frequency of this distribution is the prompt neutron decay constant, α , which at delayed critical is the ratio $-\beta_{\text{eff}}/\Lambda$. The APSD of the neutron sensitive detector's signal was estimated using an implementation of the Welch method in Python3 [11][12].

4. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

The TRISO fuel used in this experiment was originally used in the Compact Nuclear Power Source (CNPS) experiments performed at LANL between 1987 and 1991 on the Mars vertical lift machine. This fuel is now being used extensively to validate criticality calculations of HALEU systems. Each 0.87 mm diameter TRISO particle itself contains a uranium oxycarbide (UCO) kernel with ^{235}U content enriched to 19.9% by weight. This is surrounded by a carbon buffer and concentric shells of pyrolytic carbon and silicon carbide. Stacks of these fuel compacts were assembled into fuel rods 95 cm in height. The core of THETA consisted of an inner hexagonally pitched array and an outer square pitched array. The inner array is inserted or withdrawn to control reactivity by the Comet assembly. The core is reflected on its four sides by 16.8 cm of beryllium metal to decrease neutron leakage. The top and bottom of the core is axially reflected by additional graphite.

(a) Singular HALEU TRISO fuel compact enriched to 19.9% ^{235}U .

(b) Partially defueled core of THETA with top axial graphite reflector removed.

Figure 2. The inner hexagonal pitch region is moved in and out of the outer stationary square pitch region to control reactivity. Radial beryllium reflector is seen on the periphery of the square pitch region.

Table I. Specifications of the THETA Experiment and TRISO Fuel

Core Specification	Value	Fuel Specification	Value
Fuel Rods	250 - 326	Rod Length	94 cm
Moderator	Graphite	Rod Diameter	1.27 cm
Reflector	Beryllium	^{235}U Enrichment	19.9%
Reflector Thickness	16.8 cm	TRISO Packing Fraction	0.66
Square Pitch	3.55 cm	U Mass per Rod	127.8 g
Hexagonal Pitch	5.00 cm		

The inner and outer holes in the graphite moderator blocks allow for experimental flexibility and can be filled with fuel rods or interstitial materials of interest to observe how the systems criticality and kinetics parameters respond. Three configurations of the THETA experiment were diagnosed with ex-core neutron detectors to perform neutron noise analysis. Configuration 1 was considered a baseline measurement and consisted of no interstitial material. Configuration 2 included the addition of HDPE rods near in the inner core region. Configuration 3 included both HDPE and borated HDPE rods in the inner core region.

Table II. Rod Loading and Excess Reactivity for Configurations 1–3

Configuration	Fuel Rods	HDPE Rods	Borated Rods	Excess Reactivity (ρ)
1	326	0	0	17.1
2	250	18	0	11.6
3	310	18	4	23.4

Neutron multiplicity detectors known as MC-15s were used to measure fluctuations in the neutron population. These detectors, positioned 1 m from the outer beryllium reflector, consist of 15 ^3He proportional counters in a HDPE matrix and record neutron counts on a per tube basis with a timing resolution of 100 ns. The list-mode data was acquired by on board electronics and a computer located in the control room.

Figure 3. Plan view of core for the three configurations. The reflector region is omitted from these views.

The initial approaches to criticality for each configuration were performed by the inverse multiplication method ($1/M$) as a function of total number of fuel rods, and later by insertion distance of the inner movable core. When fully inserted the excess reactivity was measured using the reactor period from compensated ion chambers, and the Inhour equation as seen in Table II. Then a delayed critical state was achieved by slightly withdrawing the movable platform which increases the neutron leakage and thus decreases reactivity.

5. RESULTS

Neutron noise measurements of α for the three configurations were made at a delayed critical state ($\alpha = -\beta_{\text{eff}}/\Lambda$). High fidelity kinetics simulations of the three configurations were performed in MCNP6.3 using the KOPTS card with ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, ENDF/B-VIII.1, JEFF-3.3, and JENDL-5.0 nuclear data libraries [13][14][15][16][17]. A comparison of the simulated and experimental α values are seen in Figure 4. The uncertainties on the simulated results represent the statistical uncertainty associated with the use of the Monte Carlo method, not the uncertainty due to nuclear data. The MCNP6.3 estimations of β_{eff} did not vary from configuration to configuration. This indicated the changes in α is primarily caused by changes to Λ .

Figure 4. Experimental α values and MCNP6.3 KOPTS simulations of each configuration using various nuclear data libraries.

The solely graphite moderated Configuration 1 exhibited the largest absolute α value, while the addition

of HDPE moderator in Configuration 2 showed the lowest. This is due to the fact that Configuration 1 was undermoderated, thus the addition hydrogen increased the moderation and led to a larger Λ . Furthermore, the addition of borated HDPE in Configuration 3 caused a decrease in Λ due to the $1/v$ energy dependence of the ^{10}B and ^{11}B capture cross sections, thus increasing α .

The percent difference between each nuclear data libraries used and the experimental results are show in Figure 5. The three ENDF libraries as well JENDL-5.0 agree with one another across the three configurations. Whereas JEFF-3.3 generally underpredicts in Configurations 1 and 2.

Figure 5. Percent difference between the experimental α value and MCNP6.3 KOPTS simulations of each configuration using various nuclear data libraries.

The percentage of fissions caused by intermediate neutrons (0.625 eV - 100 KeV) was estimated by taking the mean and standard deviation of MCNP6.3 simulated values using the five aforementioned nuclear data libraries for each configuration. Plotting these values against the absolute mean difference between simulated and experimental results appears to show a general trend of increase in disagreement as the system becomes more intermediate as seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Absolute mean difference between experimental and simulated α values of configuration versus percentage of intermediate fissions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we compare experimental and simulated values of the prompt neutron decay constant α at delayed critical of three configurations of a HALEU TRISO fueled, graphite moderated system. These three configurations had differing amounts of HDPE and boron, causing noticeable changes to α due to their effects on the prompt neutron generation time, Λ . Across the three configurations and

five nuclear data libraries, all simulated results were within 5% of the experimental α values. We note a possible trend in increasing simulation error as the system becomes more intermediate. As a result of the higher sensitivity to intermediate cross section data for intermediate systems, we hypothesize this could be due to inadequacies in this cross section data. This could also be due to limitations in the MCNP6.3 KOPTS method in estimating kinetics parameters for intermediate systems. Large disagreements between experimental and KOPTS results for intermediate systems have been noted in other recent works [6][18]. Alternatively, this could demonstrate limitations in interpreting results from neutron noise methods derived from the point kinetic model where spacial effects are neglected.

The effects of differing thermal scattering treatments on simulated estimations of α is a largely unexplored topic. Since α has been shown to be very sensitive to scattering cross section data, these integral measurements may be useful for thermal scattering data validation as they have been recently used similarly in pulse neutron die away experiments [19]. This analysis would require more rigorous investigations of the uncertainty and biases associated with this experimental method and the validity of the point kinetic model for such heavily reflected systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the additional experimentalists, designers, technicians, and support personnel that contributed to the execution of the THETA experiment whom are not listed as authors. Kristin Stolte, Peter Brain, Natalie Cannon, and Nick Wynne from Los Alamos National Laboratory and Lee Hofeldt, Amy Ramirez, Ken Crow, Dave Watts, and Dominic Cotroneo IV from Mission Support and Test Services. This work was supported by the DOE Nuclear Criticality Safety Program, funded and managed by the National Nuclear Security Administration for the Department of Energy. This work was supported by the US Department of Energy through the Los Alamos National Laboratory. This work was supported by the DOE/NRC Criticality Safety for Commercial-Scale HALEU for Fuel Cycle and Transportation (DNCSH) project, a collaboration between United States Department of Energy (DOE) and the Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC), a component of the Office of Nuclear Energy's HALEU Availability Program.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. R. Brown. "A Review of In-Pile Fuel Safety Tests of TRISO Fuel Forms and Future Testing Opportunities in Non-HTGR Applications." *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, **volume 534**, p. 152139 (2020).
- [2] O. Pakari, V. Lamirand, G. Perret, L. Braun, P. Frajtag, and A. Pautz. "Current Mode Neutron Noise Measurements in the Zero Power Reactor CROCUS." *EPJ Web Conf*, **volume 170**, p. 04017 (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201817004017>.
- [3] A. dos Santos and R. Diniz. "The Evaluation of the Effective Kinetic Parameters and Reactivity of the IPEN/MB-01 Reactor for the International Reactor Physics Experiment Evaluation Project." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 178**(4), pp. 459–478 (2014). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE14-10>.
- [4] E. Gilad et al. "Sensitivity of Power Spectral Density Techniques to Numerical Parameters in Analyzing Neutron Noise Experiments." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 101**, pp. 288–298 (2017). Special Issue on the Physics of Reactors International Conference PHYSOR 2016: Unifying Theory and Experiments in the 21st Century.
- [5] B. Geslot et al. "Kinetic Parameters of the GUINEVERE Reference Configuration in VENUS-F Reactor Obtained from A Pile Noise Experiment using Rossi and Feynman Methods." In *2015 4th*

International Conference on Advancements in Nuclear Instrumentation Measurement Methods and their Applications (ANIMMA), pp. 1–6 (2015).

- [6] C. Kostelac, R. Weldon, N. Whitman, N. Thompson, T. Cutler, K. Amundson, and A. Alajo. “Neutron Noise Measurements of a Fast HEU Copper System.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering, PHYSOR 2024 Special Edition* (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2025.2471240>.
- [7] N. Thompson et al. “A New Era of Nuclear Criticality Experiments: The First 10 Years of Comet Operations at NCERC.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 195**(sup1), pp. S17–S36 (2021).
- [8] R. Sanchez et al. “Kilowatt Reactor Using Stirling Technology (KRUSTY) Component-Critical Experiments.” *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 206**(sup1), pp. S56–S67 (2020).
- [9] J. A. Kulesza et al. “MCNP Code Version 6.3.0 Theory User Manual.” Technical report, Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States) (2022). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1889957>.
- [10] “Calculation of LWR eff Kinetic Parameters: Validation on the MISTRAL Experimental Program.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 48**, pp. 51–59 (2012).
- [11] P. Welch. “The Use of fast Fourier Transform for the Estimation of Power Spectra: A Method Based on Time Averaging Over Short, Modified Periodograms.” *IEEE Transactions on Audio and Electroacoustics*, **volume 15**(2), pp. 70–73 (1967).
- [12] Python Software Foundation. *Python 3.8: Python Language Reference*. Python Software Foundation (2019). <https://docs.python.org/3.8/>.
- [13] M. Chadwick et al. “ENDF/B-VII.1 Nuclear Data for Science and Technology: Cross Sections, Covariances, Fission Product Yields and Decay Data.” *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 112**, pp. 2887–2996 (2011).
- [14] D. Brown et al. “ENDF/B-VIII.0: The 8th Major Release of the Nuclear Reaction Data Library with CIELO-project Cross Sections, New Standards and Thermal Scattering Data.” *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 148**, pp. 1 – 142 (2018). Special Issue on Nuclear Reaction Data.
- [15] N. Gustavo et al. “Progress Towards the ENDF/B-VIII.1 Release.” *EPJ Web of Conf*, **volume 294**, p. 04004 (2024).
- [16] A. J. M. Plompen et al. “The Joint evaluated Fission and Fusion Nuclear Data Library, JEFF-3.3.” *The European Physical Journal A*, **volume 56**(7), p. 181 (2020).
- [17] O. Iwamoto et al. “Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library Version 5: JENDL-5.” *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, **volume 60**(1), pp. 1–60 (2023).
- [18] G. McKenzie. “Validation of MCNP Rossi-alpha Calculations using Recent Measurements.” LA-UR-19-25525, Los Alamos National Laboratory (2019).
- [19] D. Siefman, W. Zywiec, C. Percher, and D. Heinrichs. “New Pulsed Neutron Die-Away Experiments in Light Water.” In *American Nuclear Society Summer Meeting*. Anaheim, CA, United States (2022).